

Using Public Data to Predict College Population Counts¹

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Abstract

Real-time verification of survey data can identify and correct data anomalies during data collection processes. The primary goal of this research is to use statistical modeling to predict the number of people living in a college dorm prior to the beginning of census group quarters operations using data from the Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (IPEDS) from the National Center for Education Statistics. The modeled predictions can be compared to initial college population counts collected during census operations or could be used to fill in missing college population counts after the census. Linking dorm-level census records to college-level public records to calculate predictions requires a unique college identifier. One such linking strategy uses Homeland Infrastructure Foundation-Level Data which include geographic boundary files for colleges. A college dorm from census data can be linked to a college if its geographic location falls within the college boundaries, with additional linkage based on distance to college boundaries. Once dorms are linked, the IPEDS data can be used to create predictions of college population counts that feed into real-time processing.

Key Words: Census Data, Group Quarters, Record Linkage, Geographic Files, Geospatial, Data Validation

1. Introduction

One research goal for the 2030 Census is to improve enumeration of Group Quarters (GQ), such as nursing homes, military barracks, and college/university student housing. A potential way to improve the count of these units is to develop reasonable estimates prior to enumeration so that extreme values can be flagged for review. Issues could be remedied by census representatives during data collection or could be edited after operations during data processing. To create these estimates, we can develop models by linking these GQs to publicly available data that contain additional information.

The Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (IPEDS) from the National Center for Education Statistics is an annual publicly available data system that contains information on college enrollment (as well as a multitude of other college characteristics) from 1980 to present day (U.S. Department of Education, 2019). We can use statistical modeling to predict the number of people living in college/university student housing using data from IPEDS. To link the IPEDS data to the Census, there needs to be a consistent college identifier on both datasets. However, while the IPEDS data is at the college level with a clear identifier (UNIQUEID), the census data is at the dorm level and sometimes has incomplete or inconsistent information regarding its associated college.

One method of linking census dorms to IPEDS university information uses the geographic information (i.e., latitude and longitude coordinates) on the census data along with college campus boundary polygons from Homeland Infrastructure Foundation-Level Data (HIFLD) that contain facility-level identifiers (Oak Ridge National Laboratory, 2019). We match the college dorms listed in the 2020 Census to a college if the dorm's geographic location falls within the college boundaries. We can then link each dorm to a college's UNIQUEID from the HIFLD file. Once we complete the

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linkage, we can use the IPEDS data to create models that flag initial college GQ counts from census operations that may need further review, or to fill in missing college population counts after the census.

2. Background

As outlined in Stempowski and Christy (2021), GQ operations in the 2020 Census involved two parts—advance contact and enumeration. First, each GQ was contacted in advance by phone or in person to collect information such as address updates and expected population counts. Then, GQs were enumerated in late summer (the COVID-19 pandemic delayed this operation). During post-data collection processing, reviewers identified units with insufficient information or inconsistencies, resulting in recontacting some GQs to collect additional information. Where information was still missing and the GQ was known to be occupied, the Census Bureau conducted GQ count imputation on these unresolved units. This was the first time that count imputation was used in GQ post-processing (Cantwell, 2021). For more information about the 2020 GQ imputation methodology and results, see Kennel et al. (2023). Our current research seeks to improve GQ imputation methodology and to provide an expected range of GQ counts while data collection is ongoing.

For the GQ college population, enumerations were collected for each college dorm (i.e., college/university student housing facility such as a residence hall). Dorms had to be assigned a unique identifier for the college or university during post-processing. This identifier, UNIQUEID, was assigned internally during the 2020 GQ Imputation project. Some colleges can be easy to identify by the facility name reported on the census form. However, as stated before, this field sometimes had incomplete or inconsistent information. For example, a dorm associated with the University of Pennsylvania could have varying ways of identifying the college affiliation, such as “Unviersty of Pennsylvania”, “U of P”, or “Penn”, among others, or could be left blank.

For 2030 research, two methods were developed – a statistical technique and a geospatial technique—for linking census college dorms to an appropriate UNIQUEID. The statistical technique uses the **fastLink** package in R, which is an implementation of the Fellegi-Sunter model (Fellegi and Sunter, 1969) for record linkage. The methods used by this package are described in Enamorado, Fifield, and Imai (2019). The set of dorms on the census GQ data set were matched to colleges on IPEDS data within each state using the institution name, latitude, longitude, zip code, and city. Nine passes were done through the data with slightly different model parameters in the matching, moving from more to less conservative in what was determined to be a match to IPEDS.

The geospatial technique, discussed in this paper, uses the latitude and longitude coordinates, where available, on census dorms to link to college and university campus data from HIFLD. This data is composed of all postsecondary education facilities with a population greater than or equal to 500, with an additional subset of campuses with a population under 500. The .geoJSON file from the HIFLD website contains the spatial information needed to draw the boundaries of the college data. We primarily used the R package **sf** (Pebesma and Bivand, 2023 and Pebesma, 2018), which provides support for spatial vector data, to utilize this information and match dorm points to college polygons. Once this matching is done, the data can be linked to the same UNIQUEID from IPEDS.

3. Methodology

This section illustrates the process of geographically linking college dorms to publicly available college-level data and predicting the college population in the context of a specific example of dorms in Philadelphia County. We first explain the data setup for this example, then walk through the following steps:

- 1) *Linking Step*: Develop a record linkage method that maps college dorms to their associated colleges.
- 2) *Modeling Step*: Aggregate the dorm population to the linked college and use statistical modeling to create prediction estimates and intervals for the college population.

3.1 Data Setup

We used a combination of public and fictitious data for Philadelphia County to simulate what the data would look like on a census roster. We generated a list of dorm names and latitude/longitude coordinates as the basis of our “census” by searching for “dorms in Philadelphia” in Google Maps (Google, 2024). This resulted in a list of 47 dorms. Note that this is by no means an exhaustive or completely accurate list but serves as a good illustration for how to use the methods in this paper. We also used Google to extract the true college that each of these dorms is associated with to evaluate the linkage later.

For each dorm, we fabricated previous and advance contact census counts by using a variable from IPEDS that represents the total dorm capacity of a college. Those counts were divided up among the available dorms of the true college, with some noise added. Advance contact counts were further altered with some extreme values to simulate real life scenarios where a college fails to report a population to the census, or they mistakenly list the entire population for each individual dorm. Table 1 shows a sample of the fictitious data created.

Table 1: Example of simulated census data for dorms in Philadelphia.

Dorm Name	Latitude	Longitude	True College	Simulated Previous Census Count	Simulated Advance Contact Count
North Hall	39.95871	-75.18840	DREXEL UNIVERSITY	400	410
St. Joseph Hall	40.06071	-74.98788	HOLY FAMILY UNIVERSITY	80	90
Juniper Residence Hall	39.94634	-75.16344	THE UNIVERSITY OF THE ARTS	600	0
Martin Residence Hall	39.94846	-75.15887	THOMAS JEFFERSON UNIVERSITY	500	6000
Sansom Place West	39.95469	-75.19605	UNIVERSITY OF PENNSYLVANIA	600	600

Sources: Derived from Google Maps (Google, 2024) and IPEDS (U.S. Department of Education, 2019).

3.2 Geospatial Join

Before we performed the geographic linkages, we needed to transform the coordinates from a geographic coordinate system to a projected coordinate system that better preserves the distances between spatial objects. The Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system is a popular map projecting system that contains 60 different zones and converts latitude and longitude coordinates that minimizes distortion of distances and is represented in meters (GISGeography, 2024). Zone 18N of the UTM coordinate system is the best fit for the Philadelphia region (MapTiler Team, 2024). The `st_transform()` function of the R package `sf` can be used to apply this projection.

There were two steps involved in assigning each dorm to a college polygon. First, we used the `st_join()` function from the R package `sf` to assign dorms to a college UNIQUEID if the dorm fell within the college boundaries (see the yellow dots in Figure 1). Next, if a dorm did not fall within college boundaries, we assigned the dorm to the nearest college UNIQUEID using the `st_nearest_feature()` function from the R package `sf` (see the black dots in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of colleges and dorms in Philadelphia. The yellow dots indicate dorms that fall within college boundaries. The black dots indicate dorms that fall outside of the college boundaries. Maps in this paper were created using the R package **mapview** (Appelhans et al., 2023).

Since it is possible for dorms to have a large minimum distance to the nearest dorm (e.g., 10 miles to the nearest college boundary), we set a threshold for how far we allow an assignment to a college UNIQUEID. For this research, we used 3.2 km (approximately two miles) to the nearest college boundary as the threshold for UNIQUEID assignment. Any dorm that falls outside of two miles to any college does not get assigned a UNIQUEID using this method.

3.3 Negative Binomial Modeling

Once dorm-level data was linked to a college UNIQUEID from HIFLD, we summed the previous census counts to the college level and ran statistical modeling to predict the number of people at each college using covariates from IPEDS. A reasonable model for these counts is a negative binomial model due to the overdispersion in the data; there is a large variation in college campus populations.

We started with a dataset containing every college in the IPEDS database available for the year 2019, along with 30 variables from IPEDS that were thought to be related to the counts of people living on college campuses.

We used random forest variable importance and Poisson regression with lasso variable selection to reduce the number of variables from 30 to 10 to use in modeling college counts. We performed log transformations of the continuous variables to mitigate the highly skewed distributions of these variables. We collapsed some categories of categorical variables where the categories contained few records.

Table 2: Variables from IPEDS used in modeling college population counts.

Variable Name	Variable Description
EnrFt	Total enrolled for credit full time in the fall 2019 of the academic year.
EFUGFT	Total enrolled for credit full time undergraduate.
ROOMCAP	The maximum number of students that the institution can provide residential facilities for, whether on or off campus. (off-campus dormitory space that is reserved by the institution).
ANYAIDN	Number of full-time first-time undergraduates awarded any financial aid.
GISTON2	Number living on-campus paying in state tuition 2019-20, public institutions, receiving Title IV aid.
GIS4ON2	Number living on-campus in all income levels 2019-20, public institutions, grant aid, work study aid, and loan aid.
GRNTON2	Number living on-campus 2019-20, private institutions, receiving aid.
DVEF02	Total undergraduate enrollment ages 25-64.
DVEF02	Total price for out-of-state students living on campus 2019-20.
C18SZSET	Institutions' size (student population) and residential characteristics (two or four year, residential or non-residential).

Source: IPEDS (U.S. Department of Education, 2019).

For the small example of Philadelphia, we ran a simplified negative binomial model to predict college counts using the previous simulated census count as the dependent variable and just two of the independent variables from Table 2.

$$InitialCount \sim EFUGFT + ROOMCAP$$

We used the model coefficients from this model to create prediction intervals to identify which colleges had final populations that fell beyond our expected range. We did this by first randomly drawing new parameters for the negative binomial model 1,000 times based on the initial model parameters and variances of those parameters. We then applied the resulting parameters to our observed data to generate 1,000 predictions for each college.

In this example, we selected the 10th and 90th percentiles as the lower and upper bounds of our prediction intervals. Some of the predicted upper bounds were beyond the maximum number of people that could have attended the college. In these cases, we capped the upper bound to be more realistic. If our upper bound was higher than the 12-month full-time equivalent enrollment from IPEDS, we capped the upper bound to be that count.

Once these bounds were calculated, we checked to see if the simulated advance contact count for the college fit within the prediction bounds.

4. Results

This section summarizes the results of the linking and modeling methodologies for the Philadelphia County example. Section 4.1 evaluates the geographic linkage in its assignment of UNIQUEID for

each dorm. Section 4.2 evaluates the prediction intervals from the negative binomial model and provides some examples of cases with fabricated census counts beyond the expected range.

4.1 UNIQUEID Assignment

Figure 2 displays the results of assigning college dorms to the college boundaries using the geospatial join described in Section 3.2 for the Philadelphia example. The colors of the dorm points match to the colors of the colleges to which they were assigned using the geographic linkage method.

For example, consider the selected Rashford Hall, a dorm which falls directly outside of the boundaries of Saint Joseph's University (indicated by a light green color), was assigned the UNIQUEID for Saint Joseph's University. We use the dataset compiled from Google Maps to evaluate the college assignment. For this particular example, this is a correct college assignment.

Figure 2: Map of colleges and dorms in Philadelphia. The colors of the dorm points match the colors of the colleges to which they were assigned.

Figure 3 indicates whether a dorm was assigned to the correct college UNIQUEID. A green dot indicates that the dorm was assigned to the correct UNIQUEID based on the Google Maps college assignment. Conversely, a red dot indicates that the dorm was not assigned to the correct college. In total, there were only two dorms out of the 47 total dorms that were misassigned in this Philadelphia example.

Figure 3: Map of colleges and dorms in Philadelphia. The green dots indicate a correct assignment of the dorm to UNIQUEID. The red dots indicate an incorrect assignment of the dorm to UNIQUEID.

4.2 Negative Binomial Results

Figure 4 shows the results of the prediction intervals from the negative binomial model described in Section 3.3 for the Philadelphia example. This map identifies which colleges had fictitious “census” populations from the advance contact operation that fell beyond a range of what we expected based on the model. Those colleges whose populations fell above their prediction intervals are indicated in red, while those college whose populations fell below their prediction intervals are indicated in blue. Of the 21 colleges listed in this example, two colleges’ populations fell above their prediction intervals and two colleges’ populations fell below their prediction intervals.

Figures 5 and 6 provide more details on specific colleges whose population falls outside of the predicted range. For example, Figure 5 indicates that the negative binomial model predicted that the college population of Thomas Jefferson University should be between 16 and approximately 4,559 people. IPEDS indicated that the total dorm capacity is 1,914 people. However, our fictitious census listed 7,500 people at this address, which is far above the upper bound of our prediction, indicating a need for further inspection of the dorm counts at this college. Figure 6 indicates that the negative binomial model predicted the college population of Chestnut Hill college to be between two and approximately 445 people. IPEDS indicated a total dorm capacity of 1,914 people. However, our fictitious census did not list any people at this address, indicating that the dorms for this college should undergo further review.

Figure 4: Map of colleges in Philadelphia. The red polygons indicate colleges with “census” populations above the predicted range. The blue polygons indicate colleges with populations below the predicted range. Gray polygons indicated the population fell within the predicted range.

Figure 5: Map of Thomas Jefferson University in Philadelphia. This polygon is red, indicating that the fictitious census population is above the predicted range.

Figure 6: Map of Chestnut Hill College in Philadelphia. This polygon is blue, indicating that the fictitious census population is below the predicted range.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we described a record linkage method that maps the geographical coordinates of college dorms to geographical boundaries of colleges from HIFLD. This data linkage allowed us to use statistical modeling to create prediction estimates and intervals for the college population using data from IPEDS. In practice, these predictions can be used to flag outlier college population counts collected during initial census operations or to fill in missing college population counts after the census.

Geographic data is often underutilized in the statistical field due to its complexity, but more recent tools available in R make geographic data more approachable. The method shown here is a simple and powerful tool to link data when geographic information is available. For the Philadelphia example in this paper, the geographic linking method correctly matched college dorms to colleges 96 percent of the time.

The geospatial technique has advantages where geocoding is correct and assigns the dorm within or just outside of college boundaries. It is limited if the dorm is missing geographic coordinates or is far from any college border on the HIFLD data. It could also misassign a dorm if the dorm is near multiple universities. It is also mostly limited to colleges with populations larger than 500. The statistical technique, briefly described in Section 2, may be more advantageous to use when the college has a good quality name on the file. Overall, a strategy for linking the dorms to colleges should capitalize on the advantages of both the statistical and geospatial techniques to make the most appropriate linkages.

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